

THE EFFECTS OF THE MULTI-WALLED CARBON NANOTUBE (MWNT)/CELLULOSE NANOCOMPOSITES ON THEIR PHYSICAL PROPERTIES

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Keywords: Cellulose, Multi-walled carbon nanotube, MWNT, Nanocomposite, Lyocell.

Abstract

The multi-walled carbon nanotube (MWNT)/cellulose nanocomposites were prepared using monohydrated N-methylmorpholine-N-oxide (NMMO) as a solvent for dispersing the acid-treated MWNT (A-MWNT) as well as dissolving cellulose. The A-MWNTs were well dispersed in both monohydrated NMMO and the nanocomposite films. The nanocomposite films were prepared by a film-casting method onto a glass plate. The casted films were immersed into distilled water to coagulate, and dried for a day in the sample holder. Tensile strain at break, Young's modulus, and toughness of the nanocomposite films increased ~ 5 , ~ 2 and ~ 12 times, respectively, as compared to those of the pure cellulose film by adding 0.8 wt% A-MWNT. Thermal degradation temperature and electrical conductivity of the nanocomposite film increased from 329 to 339 °C and from 2.09×10^{-5} to 3.68×10^{-3} S/cm, respectively by adding 1 wt% A-MWNT. The transmittances were 86, 69 and 55 % at 550 nm for 0.4, 0.8 and 1 wt% nanocomposite films, respectively. Thus the A-MWNT/cellulose nanocomposites (which were prepared by a so-called "Lyocell" process) were a promising material in all properties studied in this paper and can be used for many applications, such as toughened cellulose fibers, transparent electrodes, etc.

1 Introduction

The preparation of new functional materials and polymer composites containing carbon nanotubes (CNTs) is recently receiving an immense amount of attention due to their higher mechanical and thermal properties, and better electro-conductivity.[1-3] These properties of the CNTs/polymer nanocomposite depend on several factors such as the polymer system, the synthetic process used to produce CNTs, the CNT purification process,[4]

homogenous distribution of the CNTs in the polymer matrix, compatibility between the polymer and the CNTs to ensure efficient load transfer from the matrix to the CNTs, etc.[5] The major setback of the CNTs/polymer composite is the poor dispersion of the CNTs in the polymer matrix because CNTs form very stable bundles via Van der Waals' forces, resulting in the formation of hollow ropes. It is therefore very difficult to disperse CNTs using ordinary fabrication methods.[6] During the past few years a significant amount of literature has been devoted to the improvement of the adhesion[7] between the CNTs and the polymer matrix via surface modification of the CNTs, and to the choice of the polymer matrix for better compatibility with CNTs.[8] Cellulose is the most abundant regrowing organic material with outstanding mechanical properties and blendability with the foreign materials. With the discovery of the simple and environment-friendly "Lyocell" process (direct dissolution of cellulosic pulp in NMMO without chemical derivatization) for the regeneration of cellulose, much attention has been paid to cellulose in producing regenerated fibers, films, food casing, membranes, and sponges without hazardous byproducts.[9] Recently, much of the research is focused on the use of cellulose as an alternative for making the electroactive sheets[10-11] and the CNT-based nanocomposites.[12, 6]

In this article, the promising and emerging solvent of NMMO was used for preparing the A-MWNT/cellulose nanocomposite films. NMMO monohydrate was used as a solvent for dispersing acid-treated MWNTs (A-MWNTs) as well as dissolving the cellulose. The mechanical, thermal and electrical properties of the A-MWNT/cellulose nanocomposite films were reported in this paper.

2 Experimental

2.1 Materials

Cellulose powder (Buckeye Co. V-81 grade, number-averaged molecular weight (Mn) = 1200) and NMMO monohydrate (which was evaporated from 50 wt% aqueous solution of BASF[®] NMMO) were supplied by Kolon[®]. MWNTs with ~ 20 to 40 nm in diameter and ~ 30 to 40 μm in length were purchased from Nanomirae[®]. They were produced by a chemical vapor deposition (CVD) method and their carbonaceous purity was ~ 95 %. The MWNT was further purified (functionalized) with acid-treatment in 68 % of nitric acid and 98% sulfuric acid at 110 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 24 h under reflux in our laboratory. The acid-treated MWNT was denoted as the A-MWNT.

2.2 Nanocomposite preparation

NMMO in a glass tube was heated to 95 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ in an oil-bath, different amounts of the A-MWNTs were added in the tube, and the A-MWNTs in an NMMO solution were dispersed with a tip-type ultrasonicator (Vibracell, VCX-750 700W/60Hz) for 7 h. 5 wt% cellulose powders were, then, added in the A-MWNT/NMMO solution and mixed with a mechanical stirrer for 2 h. The dispersed nanocomposite dope was sonicated and mechanically stirred again for 4 and 2 h, respectively and finally degassed for 2 h. The nanocomposite films were casted on the glass and flattened into film by rolling a glass bar on the plate. The gap between the glass bar and the plate was controlled by the thickness of the rolled tape on both end-edges of the glass bar. The film on the plate was put into a water container for a day to remove NMMO, fixed into a steel frame to avoid shrinkage and dried at an ambient temperature for a day.

2.3 Characterization

The micrographs of the platinum-coated fractured surface of the A-MWNT/cellulose nanocomposite films were taken using a Hitachi S-4300 scanning electron microscope (SEM) with an accelerating voltage of 15 kV. Fourier transform infrared (FT-IR) spectra of the pristine MWNTs (P-MWNTs), the A-MWNTs, the pure cellulose and the A-MWNT/cellulose nanocomposite films were taken with an FT-IR spectrometer (FT/IR-620, Jasco co.) under vacuum. The samples were mixed with KBr and pressed into 10 mm diameter pellets. The spectra were derived from 50 co-added interferograms, which were obtained at a resolution of 1 cm^{-1} . Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) thermograms of the nanocomposite films were taken on a TGA-50 (Shimadzu co.) from 150 to 400 $^{\circ}\text{C}$

under a nitrogen atmosphere with a scan rate of 10 $^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{min}$. Tensile properties were measured with Instron 5564 (Instron co.) at 25 $^{\circ}\text{C}$. The length, width, and thickness were 30 mm, 10 mm, and 20 μm , respectively. The extension rate was set at 10 mm/min and the load cell was 5 Kgf. The conductivity of the nanocomposite films was measured at an ambient temperature with a four-point probe method using a HMS-3000 (Ecopia). The dimensions of the samples were about 10 (length) \times 10 (width) \times 0.02 (thickness) mm^3 and their ends were coated with an indium paste to ensure good electrical contact. The instrumental limit was in the range of $10^3 \sim 10^{-6}$ S/cm. Transmittance measurements were performed using a UV/visible spectrophotometer (V-650, Jasco co.).

3 Result and discussion

Figure 1 shows the IR spectra of the Pristine MWNTs (P-MWNTs), the A-MWNTs, the cellulose and the A-MWNT (0.8 wt%)/cellulose nanocomposite films. The P-MWNTs (Figure 1a) did not show any significant bands whereas the A-MWNTs (Figure 1b) showed the hydroxyl bands at 1000 ~ 1200 and 3359 ~ 3400 cm^{-1} and the carboxylic acid band at 1720 ~ 1650 cm^{-1} indicating that the acid-treatment introduced hydroxyl and carboxylic acid groups onto the MWNT surface. The cellulose (Figure 1c) showed the characteristic bands at 3359 ~ 3400 cm^{-1} (hydroxyl group), 2900 cm^{-1} (CH stretching vibration), 1430 cm^{-1} (HCH and OCH in-plane bending vibration), and 1373 cm^{-1} (CH deformation vibration). The last three bands were known to be sensitive to crystallinity.[13] The introduction of the A-MWNTs into the cellulose didn't show any changes in the band position (Figure 1d). However the intensities of the bands at 2900 and 1430 ~ 1373 cm^{-1} decreased indicating that the crystallinity might be reduced by the incorporation of the A-MWNTs in the cellulose.

Fig.1. FTIR spectra of (a) the P-MWNTs, (b) the A-MWNTs, (c) the pure lyocell film and (d) the A-MWNT(0.8 wt%)/cellulose nanocomposite film. The bands with arrows were discussed in the text.

Figures 2a-c shows the SEM micrographs of the fractured surfaces of the nanocomposite films at the amount of the A-MWNT (ϕ) = 0.8, 1 and 9 wt%. The well-dispersed A-MWNTs were observed for the 0.8 and 1 wt% nanocomposite films although the A-MWNTs in the 9 wt% nanocomposite film were entangled and poorly dispersed in several parts.

Fig.2. SEM micrographs of the fractured surfaces of the nanocomposite films at ϕ = (a) 0.8, (b) 1 and (c) 9 wt%.

Figure 3a shows the stress versus strain curves of the A-MWNT/cellulose nanocomposite films at ϕ = 0, 0.8, and 1 wt% for examples. The pure cellulose was broken before yield stress reached although the nanocomposite films was not broken but elongated more than yield strain indicating that the toughness of the nanocomposite films increased by adding a small amount of the A-MWNT in the cellulose. Figure 3b shows tensile strain at break and Young's modulus of the cellulose and the nanocomposites films as a function of the ϕ . Tensile strain at break and Young's modulus at ϕ = 0.8 wt% increased ~ 5 and ~ 2 times, respectively as compared to that of pure cellulose (ϕ = 0 wt%). Toughness (which was calculated from the area under the stress vs. strain curve in Figure 3a) at ϕ = 0.8 wt% increased 12 times as compared to that at ϕ = 0 wt%. However, further increase in the ϕ deteriorated the mechanical properties. The poorly dispersed and entangled A-MWNTs might cause the deterioration of the mechanical properties.

Fig.3. (a) Stress-stain curves at $\phi =$ (i) 0, (ii) 1, and (iii) 0.8 wt%, and (b) tensile stain at break(●) and Young's modulus(○) as a function of the ϕ .

Figure 4 shows the TGA thermograms of the A-MWNT/cellulose nanocomposites and their first derivatives with respect to temperature after complete drying in vacuum oven. The peak of the first derivatives increased as the ϕ increased indicating that the thermal stability of cellulose increased by adding a small amount of the A-MWNT; the peak temperatures for the cellulose and the 1 wt% nanocomposite film are 329, and 339 °C, respectively. The residue at 450 °C slightly increased from 27 to 31 wt% by adding 1 wt% A-MWNT.

Fig.4. (a) TGA thermograms of the A-MWNT nanocomposites and (b) the first derivatives with respect to temperature after complete drying in vacuum oven. The temperatures at arrows in (b) were discussed in the text.

Figure 5 shows the electrical conductivity, the transmittance of the nanocomposite films and those transmittance at 550 nm as a function of the ϕ . Electrical conductivity (Figure 5a) increased as the ϕ increased. The conductivity levels were between 10^{-5} to 10^{-6} S/cm at $\phi < 1$ wt% and increased to 1.77×10^{-4} and 3.07×10^{-3} S/cm at $\phi = 5$ and 9 wt%, respectively. The conductivity of the composite film which was made by melt-compounding was reported to reach a plateau of approximately 3.5×10^{-2} S/cm at high ϕ s ($\phi = 12$ wt%).[14] Figure 5b shows the transmittances at $\phi = 0, 0.4, 0.8$ and 1 wt% as a function of wavelength and Figure 5c exhibits those at 550 nm. The transmittances at 550 nm were 86, 69 and 55 % at $\phi = 0.4, 0.8$ and 1 wt%, respectively. The transparent conducting organic films has been widely used as electrode of capacitors and photodiodes,[15] electrochromic windows[16] and field effect transistors.[17] We believe that the A-MWNT/cellulose nanocomposite films might find applications in these areas.

Fig.5. (a) Electrical conductivity, (b) transmittance of the nanocomposite films (c) those at 550 nm as a function of the ϕ .

4 Conclusions

We employed NMMO monohydrate for making the toughened, thermally stable, electro-conducting and transparent A-MWNT/cellulose nanocomposite film. NMMO monohydrate was a good dispersing agent for A-MWNTs and dissolved cellulose into the

nanocomposite dope. The A-MWNT/cellulose nanocomposite films showed good mechanical properties in both tensile strain at break and Young's modulus. Toughness increased ~ 12 times by adding 0.8 wt% A-MWNT. The increase of toughness was a significant achievement in industrial applications of cellulose fiber because the brittleness of the cellulose fiber is one of the few disadvantageous properties. Thus, the A-MWNT/cellulose nanocomposites (which were prepared by so-called "Lyocell" process) were a promising material in all properties studied in this paper and can be used for many applications, such as toughened Lyocell fibers, transparent electrodes, etc.

Acknowledgements

This work was supported by the National Research Foundation of Korea Grant (2009-0073476) funded by the South Korean Government.

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